

NORDP Consultants Toolkit

A Practical Guide for Supporting Research
Capacity at Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs)
and Emerging Research Institutions (ERIs)

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About the NORDP Consultants Toolkit

This toolkit is divided into two main parts.

Part One offers an orientation to the program's history, values, goals, and theory-driven approaches that anchor our work in building a more competitive national research ecosystem, one that leverages innovation, scientific advancements, and talent from Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs) and Emerging Research Institutions (ERIs).

Part Two provides a structured roadmap for consultants supporting the Intensive Cohort model, a two-year strategy to strengthen research capacity at sixteen institutions through strategic partnerships and targeted infrastructure investments.

Each part includes consultant considerations, recommended practices, and, where available, practical tools to guide implementation.

Our goal is to offer consultants the structure and strategy needed to foster authentic, context-informed, and asset-based partnerships that support institutions in sustainably strengthening their research infrastructure and activity as a complement to consultants' individual experiences and expertise.

PART I:

A Theory-Driven Approach to Strengthen the National Research Ecosystem

Introduction

This toolkit is designed to provide structure, strategies, and theory-informed tools to help consultants support institutions in strengthening their research enterprise, especially within Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs) and Emerging Research Institutions (ERIs). It reflects the program's commitment to comprehensive, sustainable growth in the national research ecosystem.

You will notice a recurring element throughout the toolkit:

Consultant Strategy. These are prompts to help you not only think strategically and reflectively, but also to act in ways that reinforce the program's values and core assumptions about how research infrastructure is best developed, through authentic partnership, contextual understanding, and long-term institutional ownership.

This first section of the toolkit offers an orientation to the program's foundation. It includes:

- A brief history of how and why the program was created,
- A description of the different models of engagement used to serve partner institutions,
- An overview of the current consultant pool,
- And a presentation of the program's Theory of Change, which outlines how we collaboratively and sustainably grow right-sized research infrastructure.

Together, these components provide the grounding needed to approach each engagement with clarity, consistency, and purpose.

Program Origin

In 2019, the Executive Director of the White House Initiative on Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs) and the Director of the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) invited the National Organization of Research Development Professionals (NORDP) to explore strategies for strengthening research capacity and competitiveness at HBCUs. NORDP, whose mission is to advance the global capacity for and impact of research by strengthening the practice and profession of research development, was identified as a key partner in this effort.

In response, a small group of NORDP leaders submitted a proposal to the Schmidt Family Foundation via Schmidt Futures. The proposed pilot would embed four research development consultants within four HBCUs. In February 2020, with support from the NORDP Board of Directors and funding from Schmidt Futures, Dr. Kimberly Eck assumed the role of senior director and formally launched what would become the NORDP Consultants Program. In summer 2021, she mobilized a team of more than twenty NORDP volunteers to design the requests for applications for consultants, HBCU partners and evaluation team and implementation. The first cohort of four HBCUs launched in January 2022.

PROGRAM HISTORY

2019	White House OSTP and HBCU Initiative invited NORDP to explore strategies to strengthen research capacity at HBCUs.
February 2020	The NORDP Consultants Program was launched with funding from Schmidt Futures to pilot embedding research development consultants in four HBCUs.
Summer 2021	Over 20 NORDP volunteers mobilized to design application processes and implementation plans for the pilot.
January 2022	The first intensive cohort was launched with four HBCUs.
October 2022	The program receives its first research award (NSF OIA-2331578) to scale the Intensive Cohort model.
December 2022	Embedded Proposal Development Support model launched via NSF EPIIC
September 2022	Additional support through NSF Advancing Research Capacity HBCU.
December 2022	NSF EPIIC II & III funding expands embedded support model.
August 2024	First NIH-funded Partner-Initiated Proposal implemented (#1UC2GM157743-01).
September 2025	NIJ-funded partnership begins to implement the REAL Cohort program (#15PNIJ-23-GK-06158-NIJB).
March 2025	Global launch via Carnegie Corporation and IREX's UASP program. The program hosts six fellows from five African universities.

Program Growth and Funding Support

I. Intensive Cohort Model: History and Model Overview

Following the success of Cohort I, NORDP pursued expanded support through the National Science Foundation's GRANTED initiative (Growing Research Access for Nationally Transformative and Equitable Research), launched in 2022. Dr. Eck submitted a proposal to scale the NORDP Consultants Program through this new mechanism and was awarded funding under NSF OIA-2331578 in October 2023.

GRANTED was created to strengthen the U.S. research enterprise by improving the infrastructure that supports research, focusing not on science directly, but on the people, systems, and services that enable it. These include: Research Development (ideas, proposals, broader impacts); Research Administration (pre- and post-award processes); Research Data, Analytics & Tools; Technology Commercialization (tech transfer, economic development); Corporate Relations (public/private partnerships); Research Integrity/Compliance (IRB, IACUC, security); Student Research Training (STEM infrastructure); Research Communications (outreach and engagement); Research Policy (policies governing support); Research Leadership (roles like VPRs, deans, PIs).

With NSF GRANTED support, the Intensive Cohort model became a formalized two-year consulting engagement for MSIs and ERIs. Each institution, paired with a dedicated NORDP consultant team, work through a structured three-phase process to plan and implement sustainable strategies for enhancing their research infrastructure.

Key Features

- 600 hours of tailored consulting over two years
- Structured three-phase engagement framework
- \$150,000 research infrastructure investment
- Monthly peer coaching from experienced MSI and ERI leaders
- Networking with funders and research development professionals
- Professional development and networking activities

Each engagement is institutionally tailored and designed for long-term impact. Consultants co-develop strategic goals and metrics with institutional leads to ensure context-informed, sustainable growth.

II. Embedded Proposal Development Support: History and Model

To extend its impact, the NORDP Consultants Program developed the Embedded Proposal Development Support model, funded through several NSF mechanisms including NSF Enabling Partnerships to Increase Innovation Capacity (EPIIC) in December 2022, NSF Advancing Research Capacity HBCU in September 2023, and NSF EPIIC II & III in December 2023.

In this model, the program partners directly with a funding agency during an active call for proposals, embedding consultants into the applicant support process. MSIs and ERIs receive research development consulting at no cost, improving competitiveness without requiring prior funding or program participation.

Key Features

- Funded by sponsor to provide support during the application window
- Tailored for institutions applying to a specific funding program
- Consultants are embedded into the application process to support ideation through proposal development and submission

Support Activities

- Identifying key personnel and timelines
- Managing proposal development schedules
- Budget development and justification
- Drafting proposal content and supplemental documents
- Organizing reviews and preparing the submission package

This model provides real-time, hands-on support that increases proposal quality while also building internal capacity for future submissions.

III. Partner Initiated Proposals: History and Model Overview

The Partner-Initiated Proposal model allows MSIs and ERIs to proactively embed NORDP research development support into their own externally funded proposals. Institutions initiate the collaboration and include NORDP consultants as part of the project team in the proposal. If awarded, the program receives a subaward to implement the collaboratively negotiated scope of work.

Beginning in September 2025, the program partnered with John Jay College on the Center for Enhancing Research Capacity at Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs), funded by the National Institute of Justice (#15PNIJ-23-GK-06158-NIJB). Through the innovative REAL (Research Enterprise Administrators and Leaders) Cohort program, MSI research leaders engage in a 12-month virtual experience designed to foster strategic dialogue about research capacity competitiveness—filling a critical gap where existing outlets rarely address the unique needs and contexts of MSI enterprise leadership.

Key Features

- Institutions approach NORDP Consultants Program to build RD into their external proposal
- If awarded, the grant funds NORDP Consultants Program services
- Activities and timeline are aligned with the project's goals and scope

Support Activities

- Drafting proposal text describing the consultant role
- Providing letters of support or collaboration
- Serving as thought partners during planning
- Delivering strategic planning, capacity-building, or RD systems development

This model is ideal for institutions looking to embed long-term research development support into major institutional initiatives.

International Expansion

In March 2025, the Partner-Initiated model expanded globally. With sponsorship from the Carnegie Corporation of New York through the University Administration Support Program (UASP), managed by the International Research & Exchanges Board (IREX), the NORDP Consultants Program was invited to serve as a virtual host for the 2025 UASP Fellows in Research Development. The program worked with six fellows from five African universities to build knowledge and skills related to research development, institutional strategy, and global research partnerships.

Program Distinguishing Features

In addition to offering no-cost, high-impact services and building on more than a decade of field experience, the NORDP Consultants Program is powered by a research development consultant pool unmatched in breadth and depth.

NORDP consultants are senior research development professionals with expertise spanning nearly every function of the research enterprise. From grant development to compliance, and from institutional strategy to student research training, our consultants have the capacity to support institutions across the full research support lifecycle. Consultants bring strengths in implementation, development, and strategic leadership, ensuring engagements are matched to institutional goals.

Our collective expertise includes:

- Research Development (e.g., finding funding, proposal strategy, sponsor relationships)
- Training and Career Development (e.g., mentoring, grant-seeking training)
- Collaboration and Team Science
- Industry Engagement (e.g., tech transfer, start-ups, corporate sponsors)
- Research Administration (e.g., pre/post-award, proposal routing, award compliance)
- Research Compliance (e.g., IRB, IACUC, COI/COC, safety regulations)
- Research Leadership (e.g., F&A management, operational workflows, culture change)
- Research Strategy (e.g., strategic planning, benchmarking, competitive positioning)

Figure 1 illustrates the proficiency of NORDP consultants across eight skill areas spanning the research enterprise. Skills are categorized into three levels of expertise:

- **Implement** (hands-on execution and adherence to best practices),
- **Develop** (process improvement and innovation), and
- **Strategize** (vision-setting and high-level decision-making).

Each level builds on the previous one, consultants proficient at the **Develop** level are also capable of performing at the **Implement** level, and those at the **Strategize** level bring leadership and institutional alignment to their work.

The figure highlights the strategic strengths of NORDP consultants, with **Strategize**-level expertise highest in Research Strategy, Research Development, and Collaboration. These elevated levels reflect consultants' capacity for big-picture thinking, innovation leadership, and alignment with institutional goals. **Implement** and **Develop**-level expertise is especially prominent in Training & Career Development and Research Administration, underscoring consultants' broad engagement across the research enterprise. While Industry and Research Compliance show comparatively lower levels of expertise, these are specialized domains where the program may engage targeted partners and colleagues when aligned with institutional needs.

Figure 1.1: Skill Profiles of NORDP Consultants Across Key Research Enterprise Competency Areas

The current consultant pool includes:

- Four former NORDP Presidents, eight Board Members, and four NORDP Fellows
- 70% of consultants have terminal degrees including JDs, PhDs, EdDs, etc.
- Senior-level RD professionals with decades of experience in MSIs, R1s, medical schools, and federal agencies
- Thought leaders in proposal development, institutional transformation, research impact, and strategic planning

With this depth of expertise and coverage, the NORDP Consultants Program is uniquely positioned to help institutions build the research infrastructure they need, tailored to the context they have, and to do so in a way that is collaborative, intentional, and sustainable.

Right-Sized Research Capacity: Our Vision, Mission, and Approach

We envision a more competitive national research ecosystem, one that fully taps into the innovation, discoveries, and talent of Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs) and Emerging Research Institutions (ERIs).

The NORDP Consultants Program pursues research transformation with MSIs and ERIs, strengthening their institution's ability to support, sustain, and grow research activity in ways that are aligned with their mission, values, and goals. This transformation is not about replicating the strategies, structures, or policies of larger or more resourced institutions. **It is about building right-sized research capacity: capacity that fits the institution's purpose, leverages its strengths, and advances meaningful progress.**¹

This context-driven approach challenges the assumption that institutional growth should follow a single model. A strategy that works well at one university may be ineffective, or even counterproductive, at another. That's why our work begins with a deep commitment to understanding each institution's identity, culture, and context, including:

- Historical mission and strategic goals
- The relationship between research and teaching
- Community partnerships and geographic environment
- Access to special populations and local assets
- Faculty, staff, and student composition and interests
- Approaches to learning and scholarship

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What does transformation look like at this institution, not in theory, but in practice?
- How can we help the institution define success on its own terms?
- What would it mean for this institution to grow in a way that is sustainable and self-determined?

By focusing on transformation that is **right-sized**, consultants help institutions build the conditions for success, that are not only effective, but also enduring and owned by the institution itself.

This approach requires consultants to **listen deeply, observe carefully, and co-create pathways** that reflect the partner institution's own understanding of research and its role. Rather than arriving with a pre-conceived template, consultants are expected to engage in **collaborative discovery that surfaces the institution's aspirations, assets, and pain points, and helps shape infrastructure that is both realistic and transformative.**

¹ Hemming, J., & Eck, K. (2024). A Culturally Relevant Praxis: Applying participatory action research principles to support MSIs in growing research capacity. 16th Annual NORDP Research Development Conference (NORDP), Bellevue, WA, USA. National Organization of Research Development Professionals. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13357659>

A Model for Right-Sized Research Capacity

By building right-sized capacity, we strengthen the foundation for a more representative and competitive national research ecosystem, one where all institutions can contribute fully to scientific discovery and innovation from their unique strengths.

Figure 1.2: The Right-Sized Approach

We use the four-quadrant visual (shown in Figure 1.2: “A Model for Right-Sized Research Capacity”) to help institutions and consultants assess alignment:

- **Q1:** Limited resources that do not meet research needs
- **Q2:** Many resources exist but are mismatched to needs
- **Q3:** Targeted, lean resources aligned to institutional needs
- **Q4:** Fully resourced and well-aligned to enterprise needs (*a long-term goal for all Institutions of Higher Education (IHEs)*)

While Q4 represents the ideal state, many institutions may move between quadrants over time as their needs evolve. Institutions may intentionally return to Q3 to realign priorities, or shift to Q2 or Q1 as new opportunities, pressures, or leadership transitions arise. The goal is not simply more, but better, aligned, and sustainable resources.

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- Where is the institution currently in this model?
- What quadrant reflects their aspirations and what would it take to get there?
- How can we support movement toward alignment without overextension?

Right-sizing means:

- Understanding the “why” behind research at that institution
- Valuing institutional strengths, even if they differ from traditional research metrics
- Recognizing that resource intensity must be balanced with relevance and readiness
- Helping institutions define what growth on their terms looks like

Ultimately, right-sized capacity is about building the conditions for success relative to the institution’s context and goals, not replicating someone else’s infrastructure. It’s about growth that fits.

From Insight To Action: Building Toward Right-Sized, Sustainable Capacity

I. Our Position: What Is Sustainable Change?

At the core of the NORDP Consultants Program is a belief that right-sized research capacity is sustainable capacity. Sustainable capacity isn't simply about adding more, it's about aligning resources with the institutional context and goals in ways that will endure over time.

To build this kind of capacity, consultants must go beyond technical fixes. They must understand both the systems that shape research environments, and the human dynamics that drive or resist, change.

To that end, our approach blends two complementary frameworks:

**Systems Thinking + Change Management =
Sustainable, Right-Sized Growth**

When guided by participatory and collaborative methods, these strategies, used together, can help institutions achieve lasting change.

Figure 1.3: A Dual Lens for Institutional Transformation

Figure 1.3 visualizes this conceptual model, illustrating how sustainable, systemic transition, becomes possible when insight meets action, and strategy meets implementation.

- **SYSTEMS THINKING** helps us understand the broader environment: the structures, policies, cultural norms, and root causes that shape institutional behavior and outcomes.
- **CHANGE MANAGEMENT** equips us to lead the shift: to build momentum, plan strategically, and support individuals and teams in adopting new behaviors and practices.

This model serves as a foundation for the practices and tools that follow in this toolkit, offering a shared lens through which NORDP Consultants can support institutions in navigating complexity and fostering enduring progress.

II. Seeing the System: A Socio-ecological View of Research Capacity

To diagnose what’s getting in the way of growth and where to intervene, we offer a Socio-ecological Model (SEM) of Research Capacity conceptualized by Hemming and Eck (2024) (Figure 1.4).¹ This framework highlights the layers of influence that shape research success, from the political landscape all the way down to student experience.

A Socio-Ecological View of Research Capacity

¹ Hemming, J., & Eck, K. (2024). A Socio-Ecological View of Research Capacity. NORDP Consultants Program. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13756004>

What the SEM teaches us:

- Sustainable solutions require us to understand and acknowledge how these layers work together
- To effectively support change, consultants must work to illuminate the full environment, policies, people, structures, culture, and context
- Levers for impact exist at multiple levels, and research development is best positioned to directly influence:
 - Investigators
 - Research Infrastructure
 - Institutional Culture

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What layers of this system are currently enabling research?
- What layers are constraining it?
- Who experiences the impact of these constraints most directly?
- Where do I have permission, influence, or access to intervene?

III. Making Change Stick: Beckhard-Harris Change Management Formula

Understanding a system isn't enough. To build lasting change, consultants must also lead strategic, participatory shifts inside that system.

We use the Beckhard-Harris Change Formula: **(Data × Desire) × Vision × First Steps > Resistance**. This model is especially useful for our work because it explicitly names resistance and offers a framework to overcome it not by pushing harder, but by building collaborative momentum.

- **Data:** What's the evidence that change is needed?
- **Desire:** Who wants this to happen, and why does it matter to them?
- **Vision:** What's the shared picture of where we're going?
- **First Steps:** What's immediately doable that shows change is possible?

If any of these are missing, resistance wins.

Data and Desire x Vision x First Steps > Resistance

Image reproduced from Dannemiller Tyson Associates. (2000). Whole-scale change: Unleashing the magic in organizations. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

The preceding diagram illustrates common pitfalls:

- **Data but no Vision or First Steps** → *Low morale*: People understand the problems and feel the pain, but without a clear direction or actionable steps, frustration builds and energy drains.
- **Vision and Desire but no First Steps** → *Stuck in a rut*: There's motivation and a shared goal, but without tangible actions, momentum stalls and change feels out of reach.
- **Desire and First Steps but no Vision** → *“Flavor of the month”*: Action is happening, but without a unifying vision, efforts feel scattered and short-lived, lacking coherence or long-term impact.
- **Vision and First Steps but no Data** → *Wishful thinking*: There's a compelling picture of the future and some movement toward it, but without grounding in real evidence or understanding of dissatisfaction, the change may miss the mark.

A Word on Collaborative Momentum

For NORDP Consultants, this model underscores the value of balanced, participatory planning. Sustainable change isn't just about good ideas, it's about grounding them in evidence, aligning with shared purpose, and taking visible, achievable steps.

Change must be co-owned. It requires belief not just from leadership, but from those who will live with its outcomes. People need to see the effort as worthwhile and trust the process enough to move through the discomfort change brings.

Resistance isn't laziness, it's often a rational response to risk. The status quo, while imperfect, is familiar. Change demands effort, trust, and sometimes sacrifice.

Lasting change can't be imposed; it must be co-created. When people aren't brought along, they'll default to what they know. As a consultant, your role is to help others see themselves in the future you're shaping together. Resistance isn't failure, it's a signal to listen more deeply and connect more intentionally.

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- Ask early: Who needs to be at the table to feel this change belongs to them?
- How can you create moments of shared discovery rather than just pitching ideas?
- What can you do to normalize the discomfort of change and affirm the effort it takes to do something new?

IV. From Theory to Intervention: The Role of NORDP Consultants

By now, you've seen that institutions don't need everything, they need what fits. That's where you come in.

As a consultant, your role is to identify the institution's entry points for change, and help move them toward right-sized capacity through strategic interventions. Use your understanding of systems (SEM) and change management (Beckhard-Harris) to guide your approach.

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What part of the system is this intervention targeting?
- What capacity are you trying to build: technical, relational, or strategic?
- Is the intervention aligned with the institution's vision, or just your idea of what should happen?

Tools, Resources, And Frameworks

1. The [Grants Development Ecosystem Inventory](#) is a practical tool to help institutions assess their research infrastructure. Built by Research Development professionals at Predominantly Undergraduate Institutions (PUIs), it guides users through a structured reflection on existing systems, gaps, and opportunities for growth. Consultants can use this tool early in an engagement to spark conversation, surface priorities, and build shared understanding of the research support ecosystem.
2. The [Star of Success](#) is a whole scale change tool that consultants can use to help institutions examine how all parts of their research enterprise function together. It's particularly useful when institutions are working to align strategy, people, resources, and processes in pursuit of sustainable research capacity.

This framework centers around one core question:
Do we have the right conditions for success?

To answer that, the Star encourages exploration across six interconnected dimensions:

- **STRATEGIC DIRECTION:** Are we clear on our goals, value, and stakeholders?
- **FUNCTION:** Do our systems-like rewards, training, and staffing-help us do the work well?
- **FORM:** Are we organized in a way that supports collaboration and efficiency?
- **RESOURCES:** Do we have what we need (people, tools, knowledge, funding) to stay committed?
- **RELATIONSHIPS:** Are roles and power distributed in ways that support decision-making and connection?
- **SHARED INFORMATION:** Do we understand and communicate our values consistently?

The Star of Success helps shift the focus from isolated problems to patterns, making it a powerful tool for supporting right-sized, system-aware change.

PART II:

A Roadmap for a Two-Year Journey Toward Right-Sized Capacity

Introduction

This section provides a structured roadmap for consultants supporting the Intensive Cohort Model, a two-year engagement designed to build right-sized research capacity at Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs) and Emerging Research Institutions (ERIs) through strategic partnerships and targeted infrastructure investments.

At its core, the model is grounded in the belief that sustainable growth must be institutionally owned. Consultants don't deliver packaged solutions, they co-create strategies with institutional leads, honors each institution's unique mission, context, and goals.

A Quick Glance at the Model

- Two-year engagement with up to 600 hours of consulting support
- Three-phase framework: Intake → Planning → Implementation
- \$150K infrastructure investment in Year 2
- Peer coaching, cohort-based learning, and national dissemination
- Consultants act as strategic partners, capacity builders, and system navigators

What Consultants Do

- Build trust and co-develop a shared vision for research transformation
- Support institutional planning, policy, and infrastructure improvements
- Coach faculty and staff to increase research activity and confidence
- Align efforts with institutional culture, leadership, and systems
- Help embed sustainable change that lasts beyond the engagement

This section equips consultants with the tools, strategies, and frameworks to translate theory into action, supporting institutions in building research capacity that fits, lasts, and belongs to them.

The NORDP Intensive Cohort Model: A Theory Of Change For National Impact

The NORDP Intensive Cohort Model is a strategic, multi-level intervention designed to strengthen research capacity at Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs) and Emerging Research Institutions (ERIs), with the ultimate goal of enhancing the competitiveness of the national research ecosystem.

By partnering with sixteen institutions, the program surfaces insights into what it takes to expand research activity and capacity. These partnerships create opportunities for shared learning, helping us better understand how to build institutional competitiveness in a sustainable and scalable way.

Our theory of change recognizes that meaningful transformation of the national research enterprise requires coordinated action across individuals, institutions, and the broader ecosystem of research actors.

This model is a collaborative change process. It brings together consultants, project staff, and peer coaches in a dynamic structure that supports participants through:

- Tailored consulting,
- Leadership coaching, and
- Strategic resource sharing.

Each role plays a vital part in achieving the program's short- and long-term outcomes.

Strengthening Research Capacity for a Competitive National Ecosystem: The NORDP Intensive Cohort Model

	COHORT	INSTITUTION	INDIVIDUAL	NATIONAL
GOALS	1. Build right-sized research capacity at MSIs and ERIs. 2. Support sustainable, mission-aligned institutional growth.			
OBJECTIVES	Coordinate engagement and strategic program supports.	Advance institutional change through tailored, systems-aware consulting.	Strengthen leadership skills to manage change.	Share tools and knowledge to strengthen institutional and national research capacity.
ACTIVITIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitated Events & Convenings Consultant Teaming, Matching & Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess and improve systems Co-create tools and processes Coach faculty to pursue external funding Facilitate vision-setting and planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monthly coaching calls Model leadership for change Encouragement and accountability check-ins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Curating and updating the EMERGE resource library Presenting at conferences and convenings Publishing findings and lessons learned
METRICS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cohort/networking sessions; Contact hours; Engagement plans developed/revised; SMART objectives pursued 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sessions/workshops/events; Total contact hours; Participant feedback and engagement levels; Progress on SMART objectives; Self-reported grant-seeking confidence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> % participants engaged in coaching; # of coaching hours; Satisfaction with coaching; Self-reported leadership growth and confidence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # of resources; # of presentations, posters, and communications; Reach and engagement; Uptake of tools and practices
Short-Term Outcomes:	Stronger research growth strategies; Empowered research leaders; Stronger grant-seeking skills; Improved RD consulting with MSIs/ERIs.			

Long-Term Outcomes

1. Sustainably enhanced research capacity at MSIs.
2. Increased funding at MSIs and broader participating in the national research enterprise.
3. Increased access to research development knowledge tailored to the MSI/ERI context.

Key Components of the Model

1. Cohort Building & Program Facilitation

- Led by project staff, this component ensures strategic coordination, engagement, and facilitation of the cohort experience.
- Activities include convenings, investment administration, and managing consultant-participant matching and teaming.

2. Consultant-led Institutional Change

- Consultants work directly with institutional teams to assess systems, co-create tools, and coach faculty in grant development.
- Their work is grounded in systems-aware consulting and aligned with institutional SMART objectives.

3. Peer Coaching for Individual Leadership

- Peer coaches support participants in developing leadership skills and managing change within their institutions.
- Through regular coaching calls and accountability structures, they help individuals stay focused and motivated.

4. Resource Development & Dissemination

- The program curates and shares tools, practices, and findings nationally to amplify impact and build capacity across institutions.
- This includes contributions to the EMERGE resource library and presentations at national forums.

Why This Matters

By aligning efforts across these four components, the model aims to:

- Build high-level research capacity at MSIs and ERIs.
- Sustainably enhance institutional research growth.

Increase access to research development knowledge tailored to the unique contexts of participating institutions.

As a consultant, you are a key driver of this change. Your work supports not only the institutions you serve but also contributes to a broader movement toward equity and excellence in the national research enterprise.

How Consultants Support Right-Sized Research Capacity

The Intensive Cohort Model is grounded in a systems-based theory of change: to sustainably grow research capacity, we must understand the system that supports research activity at a partnering institution. This means that we explore multiple levels of influence—people, policies, structures, and culture to align our efforts with each institution’s unique context, identity, and goals.

I. Understanding Research Culture as the Foundation for Change

Before we can support research transformation, we must **first understand the cultural context in which research lives at our partnering institutions.**

Institutions are not just systems of policies and structures, they are communities shaped by shared values, histories, and identities. Culture is the lens through which people interpret meaning, make decisions, and respond to change.

In our work, cultural resistance is often the most powerful, and least visible, barrier to transformation. Culture is seldom codified, but it is deeply felt. **It shapes how research is prioritized, how success is defined, and how individuals engage with institutional goals.**

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

To support meaningful change, consultants explore:

- How is research expressed as part of this institution’s broader culture?
- What values, beliefs, or assumptions might shape how research is perceived or practiced here?
- What cultural tensions might arise as we introduce new ideas or strategies?

We adapted Tierney and Lanford’s framework for Institutional Culture in Higher Education (2018)¹ to help answer the above questions to explore an institution’s research culture. We identified six dimensions that shape how research may be embedded in institutional life:

1. **MISSION** – How is research positioned as a core institutional priority?
2. **ENVIRONMENT** – How does research connect to the institution’s community, peers, and funding landscape?
3. **SOCIALIZATION** – What values and traits are reinforced through research-related roles and norms?
4. **INFORMATION** – How is research communicated internally and externally? What language is used?
5. **STRATEGY** – How is research integrated into decision-making and governance?
6. **LEADERSHIP** – How do formal and informal leaders build trust and guide research-related change?

These dimensions offer a cultural map, a way to understand how research is perceived, supported, and sustained within the institution. They may also help consultants identify where alignment exists, where tensions may arise, and how to frame change in ways that resonate with institutional identity.

¹ Tierney, W. G., & Lanford, M. (2018). Institutional Culture in Higher Education. In Encyclopedia of International Higher Education Systems and Institutions (pp. 1–9). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9553-1_544-1

II. What Do We Mean by Research Transformation?

In the NORDP Consultants Program, we define research transformation as the process of strengthening an institution's ability to support, sustain, and grow research activity in ways that are aligned with its mission, values, and context. It is not about replicating the structures of larger or more resourced institutions; it is about building right-sized capacity that fits and lasts.

Research transformation is not a single intervention or outcome. It is a cumulative shift in how research is understood, valued, supported, and practiced across the institution. It involves:

- Strategic alignment between research goals and institutional priorities
- Cultural integration of research into the identity and daily life of the institution
- Operational improvements in systems, staffing, and processes
- Expanded participation in research activity across faculty, staff, and students
- Increased confidence and capability among leaders and investigators to pursue funding and manage change

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What does transformation look like here, not in general, but at this institution?
- How can we help the institution define success on its own terms?
- What would it mean for this institution to grow in a way that is sustainable and self-determined?

III. Where Change Happens: A Socio-ecological View of Research Capacity

Once we understand how research is culturally situated, the next question becomes:

Where can we act to support transformation?

The Socio-ecological Model (SEM) of Research Capacity (Hemming and Eck, 2024)² offers a practical framework for answering that question. It helps you as consultants identify the layers of influence where research culture is enacted and where change can be exercised. These layers are not isolated, they interact and reinforce one another. Change in one area often requires, or enables, change in others.

² Hemming, J., & Eck, K. (2024). A Socio-Ecological View of Research Capacity. NORDP Consultants Program. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13756004>

Layers of Influence in the Research Enterprise

1. Research Leadership

Leaders shape vision, set incentives, and make strategic decisions. Consultants support leadership by building trusted relationships, helping clarify goals, and offering models for managing change.

Strategy Questions:

- What motivates this institution's leaders to invest in research?
- How do they define success, and what do they need to lead change confidently?

2. Personnel & Systems

Staff and workflows are the operational backbone of the research enterprise. Consultants can help improve grants management, streamline processes, and build staff capacity through training and coaching.

Strategy Questions:

- Where are staff roles unclear or under-supported?
- What systems are creating friction or inefficiency?

3. Policy & Processes

Institutional policies and procedures shape how research is conducted and supported. Consultants can work with partners to identify gaps, refine policies, and align processes with strategic goals.

Strategy Questions:

- What policies are outdated, unclear, or misaligned with research goals?
- Who has the authority to change them, and who needs to be brought along?

4. Faculty/Investigators

Faculty are the drivers of research activity. Consultants can provide one-on-one proposal support, research career coaching, and opportunities for collaboration and peer learning.

Strategy Questions:

- What do faculty need to feel confident pursuing funding?
- How are early-career researchers being supported?

5. Culture & Communication

How research is talked about matters. Consultants can help institutions craft internal messaging, elevate research success stories, and build internal buy-in for research as a shared priority.

Strategy Questions:

- What messages about research are being communicated, explicitly or implicitly?
- Who is telling the story of research on campus?

6. Infrastructure

Systems like IRBs, eRA platforms, and shared facilities are essential to research operations. Consultants can help assess needs, guide investments, and support implementation of new tools and structures.

Strategy Questions:

- What infrastructure gaps are limiting research activity?
- How can we align infrastructure investments with strategic goals?

Consultant Roles and Responsibilities

I. A Collaborative, Systems-Aware Approach

As NORDP Consultants, you are not just subject matter experts, you are strategic partners working alongside institutional leaders to co-create a vision for right-sized research capacity and help bring that vision to life.

You enter each engagement with humility and respect, committed to **building authentic, equal partnerships** that honor each institution's legitimacy, integrity, and identity. The goal is not to replicate a standard model, but to **unlock and organize the institution's own potential** for growth.

The model illustrated in *Figure 2.1: A Vision for Participatory-Based Engagement to Unleash Power* captures this approach. It shows how your research development expertise, funding strategy, systems design, policy, and planning, is best paired with institutional knowledge, rooted in mission, community, and context. At this intersection lies the potential for **sustainably increased research infrastructure and activity**.

A Vision for Participatory-based Engagement to Unleash Power

Desired approach: Respectfully enter to build **authentic, equal partnerships** and **networks of learning and mutual support** to **sustainably enhance research infrastructure and capacity** honoring each institution's unique legitimacy, integrity, and identity.

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What strengths and insights does the lead partner bring to this engagement?
- How can we ensure our strategies are grounded in institutional knowledge, not external assumptions?
- What does it mean to be a respectful visitor in this institution's story?

II. Navigating the System to Support Change?

As an external observer, you have the unique ability to move across layers of the research enterprise, illuminating patterns, identifying leverage points and helping institutions see themselves more clearly. Your role is to:

- **Illuminate the system:** Help institutions see how different layers interact and where change is possible.
- **Co-create interventions:** Design strategies that are context-specific and culturally aligned.
- **Build capacity:** Strengthen the people, processes, and tools that support research activity.
- **Strengthen momentum:** Help embed change into institutional routines, roles, and relationships.

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- Where is the institution already moving, and how can we support that momentum?
- What's the smallest meaningful step we can take to build trust and demonstrate progress?
- How do we ensure the work we do together lasts beyond our engagement?

III. Who Are NORDP Consultants?

NORDP Consultants are vetted research development professionals with deep experience across the research enterprise. They demonstrate a commitment to equity, capacity-building, and the mission of the program. Consultants bring a wide range of research enterprise expertise in areas such as:

- Research development and proposal strategy
- Collaboration and team science facilitation
- Training and career development for faculty and staff
- Strategic research planning and institutional alignment
- Research administration and operational improvement
- Research leadership and culture change

Consultants are matched in teams of two or three, with complementary skills and shared responsibility for delivering up to 600 hours of consulting support over two years.

IV. Typical Activities

NORDP Consultants support institutional transformation through two primary categories of activity, each aligned with the program's three-phase engagement framework designed to build sustainable, right-sized research capacity.

Category 1: Strengthening Infrastructure and Expanding Institutional Capacity

This category focuses on improving the systems, policies, and resources that support the research enterprise. Consultants work collaboratively with institutional leads to:

- **ASSESS AND PLAN:** Conduct environmental scans, stakeholder mapping, and institutional asset reviews to identify strengths, gaps, and stretch goals.
- **BENCHMARK:** Compare institutional performance to aspirational peers to inform strategy and operations.
- **DEVELOP POLICY:** Refine or create policies that support research growth and alignment with institutional goals.
- **IMPROVE OPERATIONS:** Support implementation of standard operating procedures (SOPs), grants management systems, and process enhancements (e.g., proposal routing, compliance workflows).
- **BUILD RESOURCES:** Develop tools, templates, and internal guides to support research activity.
- **FACILITATE PEER LEARNING:** Promote collaboration and shared learning across institutions.
- **SUPPORT STAFF DEVELOPMENT:** Provide coaching and training to expand staff capacity and institutional knowledge.

Category 2: Building Pathways to Increased Research Activity

This category focuses on enhancing the knowledge, skills, and confidence of faculty and staff to pursue and manage research funding.

Consultants provide:

- **PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT SUPPORT:** One-on-one coaching to help faculty craft competitive proposals.
- **RESEARCH CAREER COACHING:** Guidance on research planning, collaboration, and long-term career development.
- **WORKSHOPS AND TRAININGS:** Sessions on funder landscapes, grant writing, proposal review, and research strategy.

V. Who Do Consultants Work With?

As a consultant in the NORDP Intensive Cohort Model, you're part of a collaborative structure designed to drive institutional transformation. You'll work closely with key partners, each playing a vital role in advancing research capacity at MSIs and ERIs.

1. Lead Partners

Your primary institutional collaborators. These are senior leaders at each participating MSI/ERI who:

- Possess institutional knowledge and either positional or empowered authority.
- Can influence key domains like infrastructure, process, policy, people, resources, and information.
- Are responsible for driving institutional engagement and championing change on campus.

You'll partner with them to:

- Co-develop and implement the Engagement Plan.
- Shape the strategy for the \$150K infrastructure investment.
- Align consulting activities with institutional priorities and SMART objectives.

2. Peer Coaches

Seasoned research development professionals who:

- Provide monthly coaching to institutional participants beginning in year 1, quarter 2.
- Offer encouragement, accountability, and leadership modeling.

While you won't directly manage coaching, their insights can inform your consulting strategy and help you understand participant progress and challenges.

3. Program Staff

Your operational and strategic backbone. Program staff:

- Facilitate shared learning across the cohort.
- Administer the \$150K investment process.
- Coordinate consultant matching, teaming and management.
- Manage the development and dissemination of resources through the EMERGE Library.
- Organize key events like:
 - o Quarterly Networking Events for Leads
 - o Monthly Consultant Check-ins
 - o Annual Meeting
 - o All-Hands Convenings

You'll collaborate with them to:

- Stay aligned with program goals and timelines.
- Access tools, templates, and resources to support consulting.
- Complete evaluation activities.
- Troubleshoot challenges and share emerging strategies.

4. Fellow Consultants

You're part of a cohort of consultants working across institutions. This peer network:

- Offers opportunities for shared strategy development.
- Supports customization of research development approaches for different institutional contexts.
- Encourages cross-consultant learning and collaboration.

VI. Key Deliverables

As a consultant, your contributions are structured and measurable. You are expected to:

- Engagement Plan & Quarterly Updates

Co-develop a strategic plan with your Lead Partner to guide institutional engagement, aligned with SMART objectives and updated quarterly.

- Evaluation & Activity Tracking

Document your consulting hours, activities, and outcomes to support program-wide learning and accountability.

- Support for \$150K Infrastructure Investment

Collaborate with institutional leads to shape the narrative, scope of work, and budget justification for the Year 2 investment.

- Monthly Consultant Cohort Meetings

Participate in monthly meetings with program staff and fellow consultants to share strategies, troubleshoot challenges, and learn together as a cohort.

Three-Phase Engagement Strategy

The Intensive Cohort model is structured around a three-phase engagement framework that guides consultants and institutional partners through a two-year journey of discovery, planning, implementation, and sustainability. This framework is grounded in the understanding that lasting change requires more than good ideas—it requires trust, shared vision, and actionable steps.

Using the Beckhard-Harris Change Formula, each phase aligns with a key component of sustainable change:

- **Phase I: Intake** → Data and Desire
- **Phase II: Planning** → Vision
- **Phase III: Implementation** → First Steps

Throughout all phases, consultants must remain attentive to resistance—not as a sign of failure, but as a signal that more listening, alignment, or trust-building may be needed. Institutions are not blank slates; they have already started on their research transformation journey. The Consultant Program is just one actor in a larger story arc, and so consultants must be grounded in the institutional lead’s knowledge, relationships, and context.

Phase IA: Consultant Team Pre-Work

Purpose:

Before engaging with institutional partners, consultants begin by building trust and alignment within their own team and deepening their understanding of the institutional context. This phase sets the tone for a respectful, collaborative engagement grounded in respect of each other, the institution and shared purpose.

Key Activities:

- Build relationships and clarify team roles, working styles, and communication preferences.
- Explore each consultant's relevant experience and skills, especially those aligned with the institution's goals and context.
- Review publicly available institutional materials (e.g., websites, annual reports, HERD data, strategic plans).
- Investigate the historical, social, and policy contexts that shape the institution's research environment and identity.

Consultant Strategy - Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What do we know about this institution's mission, history, and community role?
- How does the institution's identity shape its approach to research and student learning?
- How does the institution communicate its research impacts and assets? What has been recently published in news outlets about the institution?
- What assumptions might we need to unlearn before we begin?
- What collective experience do we have working with similar institutions?
- What strengths, skills, and perspectives does each consultant bring to this engagement?

Phase IB: Intake, Relationship Building & Discovery (Months 1–3)

Purpose:

This phase is about building trust, surfacing institutional knowledge, and assessing readiness for change. Consultants begin to understand the institution's context, assets, and aspirations, laying the groundwork for shared goals and institutional buy-in.

Key Activities:

- Conduct environmental scans and document reviews (strategic plans, HERD data, proposal/award history, etc.)
- Interview key stakeholders (e.g., VPRs, deans, faculty leaders)
- Map influence and decision-making structures
- Begin drafting SMART objectives collaboratively

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What evidence (data) shows where change is needed or desired?
- Who wants this change, and why does it matter to them?
- What are the institution's existing strengths and assets?
- Who holds formal and informal power to influence change?
- What relationships do we need to build to foster trust and shared ownership?
- Where might resistance show up, and what might be driving it?
- Who sets or influences research strategy?
- Where do policies or systems sit (inside or outside of research office)?
- Where can you support indirect influence (e.g., via faculty or shared services)?

Phase II: Collaborative Planning (Months 4–6)

Purpose:

This phase is about co-creating a shared vision for right-sized research capacity. Consultants and institutional leads synthesize what was learned in Phase I and translate it into a strategic roadmap.

Key Activities:

- Finalize the Engagement Plan and SMART objectives
- Align the \$150K infrastructure investment with institutional goals
- Identify evaluation indicators and stakeholder engagement strategies
- Refine priorities and timelines collaboratively

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What does success look like for this institution, and who defines it?
- How do we ensure this vision reflects institutional identity and context?
- Are we building a plan with the institution, not for it?
- Can the institution act on the vision with its current structure?
- How do we ensure the vision is compelling enough to overcome resistance?
- What language are we using to describe the future, and is it inspiring and asset-based?

Phase IIIA: Implementation (Months 7–18)

Purpose:

This is the action phase—where consultants help institutions take visible, achievable steps that demonstrate progress, build momentum, and begin embedding change into systems and culture.

Key Activities:

- Deliver trainings, 1:1 consultations, and peer learning activities
- Facilitate improvements in infrastructure, staffing, policy, and processes
- Support proposal planning, compliance updates, and tool development
- Guide institutional communication about the research enterprise
- Provide input on the \$150K infrastructure investment execution
- Revisit and revise the Engagement Plan quarterly

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What small wins can we help the institution achieve early?
- How are we helping the institution build confidence in its own capacity?
- Where is resistance still showing up, and what might it be telling us?
- How are we embedding change into systems, roles, and culture?
- What will remain after we leave, and who will carry it forward?

Phase IIIB: Reflection & Sustainability (Months 19–24)

Purpose:

This phase is about consolidating progress, documenting lessons, and preparing the institution to sustain and grow its research capacity beyond the engagement.

Key Activities:

- Revisit the Engagement Plan and assess completion of SMART objectives
- Co-document lessons learned and ongoing institutional needs
- Support sustainability planning: embedding roles, policies, and tools
- Prepare for year-end reporting and closeout
- Identify legacy opportunities: internal champions, external positioning, or future proposals

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What have we learned, and how can we make it useful to the institution?
- What systems or roles need to be formalized to sustain progress?
- Who are the internal champions who will carry this work forward?
- How can we help the institution tell its story of change?
- What resistance remains, and how can we help the institution navigate it after we leave?

Navigating Complexity and Building Buy-In

Consultants in the NORDP Intensive Cohort Model operate in dynamic environments. Resistance, shifting priorities, and unclear authority are not signs of failure, they are signs of complexity. Your role is to navigate this complexity with flexibility, curiosity, and strategic insight.

I. Building Trust and Institutional Buy-In

The steps taken early in the relationship are essential to building momentum and trust. Successful consultants intentionally cultivate relationships, clarify authority, and adapt to institutional realities:

- **TRAVEL EARLY AND OFTEN** In-person visits build trust, deepen relationships, and provide valuable context for problem-solving.
- **UNDERSTAND THE LEAD'S INFLUENCE** Assess the institutional lead's network. Their relationships can accelerate or inhibit progress.
- **MAP FORMAL AND INFORMAL STRUCTURES** Use organizational charts and trust-based conversations to understand reporting lines and hidden dynamics. Identify who can act, block, or champion across infrastructure, policy, people, and resources.
- **PRESENT TO POWER BROKERS** Engage both formal decision-makers and informal influencers early—including skeptics with relational power.
- **SOCIALIZE THE PROGRAM** Beyond the Lead Broaden engagement across departments. Encourage shared responsibility and build institutional capacity.
- **CO-CREATE, DON'T DICTATE** Use open-ended questions to surface institutional solutions. Build ownership and sustainability.
- **ASSESS THE LANDSCAPE** Identify existing strengths in research support. Build on what's working.
- **HONOR INSTITUTIONAL RHYTHMS** Align your engagement with the institution's calendar and cadence. Timing matters.
- **EXPECT LEADERSHIP CHANGES** Be prepared to reframe your work and reintroduce program value as leadership evolves.

II. Navigating Common Challenges in Underfunded Research Environments

Institutions experiencing chronic underfunding often face structural constraints that shape the pace and scope of change. Consultants must set realistic expectations and apply strategic insight to help institutions grow in ways that are sustainable given their resource constraints.

Challenge	How to Detect	Adaptive Strategy
Unclear Authority	Review organizational charts and ask about informal influence	Map formal and informal decision-making roles.
Resistance to Change	Use the Beckhard-Harris Formula to identify gaps in readiness.	Explore what resistance may be protecting.
Competing Priorities	Ask about strategic plans and timelines.	Align with institutional goals; stay flexible.
Leadership Turnover	Look for frequent changes or interim roles in key positions.	Reintroduce program value and adapt to new priorities.
Unfilled or Overloaded Roles	Request org charts; note broad scopes or missing functions.	Identify gaps and advocate for strategic staffing.
Weak Infrastructure	Ask about key processes and system integration.	Use data to surface inefficiencies and depersonalize feedback.
Deferred Maintenance & Tech	Observe facilities; ask about IT and equipment cycles.	Connect infrastructure needs to research capacity.
Limited Staff Development	Ask about training budgets and conference support.	Link professional growth to institutional effectiveness.
Temporary Fixes as Norm	Listen for “making do” or long-term “temporary” solutions.	Promote sustainable systems over short-term patches.

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

Use these reflective questions to adapt your strategy in real time:

- What assumptions am I making about how decisions are made here?
- Where is resistance showing up, and what might it be protecting?
- How can I adapt my approach without compromising the institution's ownership of the work?
- Who needs to be in the room—even if they don't have a formal title?
- What's the rhythm of this institution, and how can I align with it?

III. Quick Reference: Early Lessons from the Field

Consultants who succeed tend to:

- **BUILD TRUST INTENTIONALLY**
Trust enables candid conversations and meaningful change. Demonstrate care, competence, and authenticity.
- **CLARIFY AUTHORITY EARLY**
Understand who can implement change and who influences decisions behind the scenes.
- **SECURE BUY-IN ACROSS ROLES**
Engage leadership across research and academic domains. Broaden program awareness to build resilience.
- **LEVERAGE THE LEAD'S NETWORK**
Encourage the lead to convene key players and navigate silos using their institutional relationships.
- **UNDERSTAND LEADERSHIP DYNAMICS**
Monitor alignment between research and institutional leaders. Adjust your strategy accordingly.
- **ADAPT TO INSTITUTIONAL FLUX**
Use structure and relationships to stay grounded amid churn and shifting priorities.
- **TAILOR YOUR APPROACH**
Reflect the institution's unique structure, culture, and resource realities—not idealized models.

Learning As You Go: Using Evaluation To Strengthen Impact

Evaluation is seen as a tool for learning, adaptation, and strategic reflection. As a consultant, the evaluation activities help us refine the approach, support institutional partners more effectively, and contribute to the broader learning of the cohort.

Why It Matters

The goal of this program is progress, not perfection. That means learning about institutional context, uncovering barriers, and identifying what's not working is just as valuable as celebrating wins. Evaluation helps surface these insights and ensures they inform your next steps.

Consultant Evaluation Responsibilities

You are expected to:

- **SUBMIT QUARTERLY REFLECTIONS AND ACTIVITY UPDATES**
Document progress, shifts in context, and what you're learning, especially about institutional readiness, capacity, and engagement.
- **PARTICIPATE IN MIDPOINT AND FINAL INTERVIEWS**
Reflect on your consulting approach, institutional dynamics, and lessons that could inform future engagements.
- **USE SMART OBJECTIVES TO TRACK PROGRESS**
Collaboratively define and revise goals with your institutional lead. Update them as needed to reflect evolving priorities or new insights.
- **USE EVALUATION AS A STRATEGIC CHECK-IN TOOL**
Use quarterly updates as an opportunity to revisit goals with your lead partner, assess alignment, and discuss whether strategies or timelines need to shift.

Consultant Strategy – Questions to Guide Your Approach:

- What am I learning about my own skills and approach?
- What am I learning about this institution's readiness and capacity?
- How can I use evaluation data to adjust my strategy?
- What insights might be useful to share with the broader cohort or field?
- What contextual shifts (e.g., leadership changes, new priorities) are influencing our progress?
- How can I use this reflection to re-engage or re-align with institutional leadership?

Tools, Resources, and Frameworks

1. The **NORDP Consultants Engagement Plan (Appendix A)** is a collaborative tool that guides and documents the evolving work between the lead and their consulting team. Updated quarterly, it helps set SMART objectives, track progress, and reflect on contextual shifts that influence research transformation. The plan captures institutional progress over time, highlighting both accomplishments and changing conditions. The consultants and leads review and update their plans quarterly to ensure the work remains responsive, strategic, and aligned with long-term goals for sustainable research capacity.
2. The **WANDER Institutional Assessment** is an adaptable tool designed to help institutions reflect on the full scope of their research ecosystem—from pre- and post-award processes to compliance, communications, technology, and organizational development. For NORDP consultants, it offers a structured way to uncover how research support is organized, where gaps exist, and what contextual factors shape institutional capacity. The tool can help surface both operational realities and strategic aspirations. Consultants can use it to guide early conversations, and tailor support to institutional needs, making it a valuable companion to the Engagement Plan.
3. The **WANDER Research Climate Survey** may be administered to assess faculty and staff experiences with research administration, including grant support, communication, training, and institutional policies. Developed under the WANDER GRANTED Planning Grant, it captures both satisfaction levels and barriers to engagement across the research lifecycle. For NORDP consultants, this tool can be used to gather anonymous, institution-wide feedback early in an engagement. It helps surface perceptions, identify systemic challenges, and inform strategies that are responsive to the lived experiences of research stakeholders.
4. The **SUNDRI Survey** is a research-informed tool designed to help institutions reflect on how research development is structured and supported, particularly at under-resourced four-year colleges and universities. For NORDP consultants, it offers a way to explore the networks, staffing, and coordination that shape proposal development and grant management. Like the WANDER tool, SUNDRI can guide early conversations about infrastructure and capacity, helping tailor support to institutional realities and aspirations.

Appendix A – Engagement Plan

NORDP Consultant Program Planning Instructions and Example

About the Engagement Plan

This engagement plan captures your goals, activities, and evolving context in alignment with the NORDP Consultants Program theory of change. This theory takes a socio-ecological view of an institution's research capacity, applies change management as a core level for opportunity, emphasizes culturally responsive research development practices, and aims for long-term self-directed institutional sufficiency and sustainability.

Consultants typically support institutions through two mutually reinforcing pathways:

- **Improving Infrastructure and Expanding Institutional Capacity:**
Working with leadership and staff to strengthen systems, align resources, enhance staffing, and improve internal processes that support a robust research enterprise.
- **Building Pathways to Increased Research Activity:**
Supporting faculty engagement, strengthening proposal development systems, and fostering a research culture that values and rewards grant-seeking.

Each engagement may emphasize one or both pathways depending on institutional context, needs, and readiness. This plan should reflect how these pathways are being advanced and be completed collaboratively with the MSI leads. It should be updated quarterly and used as a tool to document priorities, track change over time, and surface the facilitators and barriers that shape the institutional research development journey.

Instructions for Completing the Engagement Table

This table is a working document designed to help you and the MSI lead collaboratively define, refine, and track progress on key research development priorities.

What to Complete:

You are only required to complete the "Prompts" column.

What the "Guiding Questions" Are For:

Each section includes a set of guiding questions to help focus your thinking and conversations with institutional partners. These do not need to be filled out or submitted but are there to support a more thoughtful, context-aware response.

How to Use This:

- Complete the prompts collaboratively with the MSI lead.
- Submit Initial engagement plans by Month 6 (March 2026 for the 2025 cohort and March 2027 for the 2026 cohort).
- Revisit and revise as needed in your quarterly updates to reflect new learning or shifts in context or goals.

- If a SMART Objective changes, archive the old one in the Quarterly Progress Notes section and explain the rationale.

How Many Objectives to Include:

- For a two-year engagement, four to five SMART objectives is standard. Fewer may be appropriate for institutions with narrower focus areas or limited bandwidth; more may be reasonable for institutions with broad buy-in and multiple change efforts.

Quarterly Updates:

Each quarter, consultants and lead partners should review progress toward the stated objectives. Consultants will submit a brief written update that reflects progress made, any contextual changes, and emerging opportunities or concerns. It is expected that SMART objectives may evolve over time based on implementation experience. These shifts, and the insights gained from them, are considered a valuable outcome of the engagement.

Component	Prompt	Guiding Questions
SMART Objective:	Define one specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, time-bound objective aimed at increasing participation in research, research capacity, research development capacity, and/or broadening participation in research. Goal setting assistance.	<p>What specific change do you aim to achieve in this engagement?</p> <p>Who will benefit, and how?</p> <p>Is this goal focused on a short-term result, or long-term systems change?</p>
Metric(s):	Identify 2 to 3 metrics that indicate progress. At least one should be quantitative.	<p>How will you know if you're making progress?</p> <p>What data already exists or needs to be created to track this?</p>
Baseline Metric(s):	Document the current state using qualitative or quantitative information.	<p>What is the current state of capacity or performance related to this objective?</p> <p>What institutional policies, practices, or norms exist?</p>
Year 1 Milestone:	List 1 to 3 realistic milestones for the first year. These can align with your metrics or go beyond them.	
Year 2 Milestone:	List 1 to 3 milestones you hope to achieve by the end of the second year.	
Major Activities:	Describe key activities you (the consultant) and the MSI leads will pursue to reach the objective.	<p>Will the consultants be providing expert advice?</p> <p>Or are the consultants acting as a capacity-expander (completing tasks that the lead needs)?</p>

Component	Prompt	Guiding Questions
Sustainability Plan:	Explain how the institution will maintain or scale this work beyond the life of the engagement.	<p>What systems or staff need to be in place?</p> <p>What capacity or momentum is being built?</p> <p>What funding or partnerships might support long-term continuation?</p>
Contextual Info:	<p>Describe environmental, organizational, or relational factors that influence success or create tension in the work. Be thorough. This helps us understand what's driving (or blocking) change.</p> <p>Include where applicable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recent leadership changes (e.g., new provost) Shifts in institutional priorities (e.g., strategic plan, realignment, budget crises) Barriers (e.g., limited time, lack of internal RD expertise, IT challenges) Enablers (e.g., high-level champions, institutional momentum, recent policy changes) Cultural considerations (e.g., institutional trust, community decision-making norms) 	<p>How are decisions being made?</p> <p>What are the formal and informal systems that affect RD work?</p> <p>What internal narratives or assumptions are at play?</p>
<p>Quarterly Updates: Enter the reporting period dates and duplicate this section as a new row as needed for each new quarter.</p>	<p>A: Has the SMART Objective Changed?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If YES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Previous SMART Objective (Archived): Copy and paste the original SMART objective here. Rationale for change Briefly explain what prompted the shift (e.g., leadership turnover, new institutional priority, loss of capacity, faster-than-expected progress). New SMART Objective: Enter the updated objective following the SMART format. Are metrics and milestones also changing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No 	<p>B. Are any of the following components also being adjusted this quarter?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Metrics</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Milestones</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Major Activities</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Sustainability Plan</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Contextual Information</p> <p><i>If any are checked, please update the relevant sections and briefly explain below what changed and why.</i></p> <p>C. Emerging Learning Use this space to reflect on what you're learning about the institution, about your consulting role, or about what's needed to make this work successful.</p>

Example

Component	Description
SMART Objective:	Submit five NSF CAREER proposals annually.
Metric(s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ # of NSF CAREER proposal submissions▪ # of participants in NSF CAREER Bootcamp
Baseline Metric(s):	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 1 NSF CAREER proposal submission in FY21▪ 0 participants in NSF CAREER Bootcamp
Year 1 Milestone:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Invite 100% of eligible faculty to participate in Bootcamp▪ 10 participants in NSF CAREER Bootcamp▪ Submit 3 NSF CARRER Proposals
Year 2 Milestone:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Invite 100% of eligible faculty to participate in Bootcamp▪ 11 participants in NSF CAREER Bootcamp▪ Submit 5 NSF CARRER Proposals
Major Activities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Develop systematic process to identify eligible faculty▪ Develop templates for inviting faculty to participate in Bootcamp▪ Adopt and refine NSF CAREER Bootcamp curriculum▪ Offer NSF CAREER Bootcamp annually
Sustainability Plan:	The SOP for identifying faculty, inviting them to participate, and curriculum will be developed in Year 1 and used for the foreseeable future. The Associate Dean for Research from the College of Arts & Sciences will attend the NSF CAREER Bootcamp session in Year 1. She will co-present the Bootcamp in Year 2 with the intention of presenting it annually in the future herself.
Contextual Info:	The institution has never held an NSF CAREER Bootcamp before and has few NSF proposals. The president has set a goal to expand the institution's reach into NSF. Early career faculty are aware of the program but have not received training in applying. Administration expects faculty to be receptive to participating in the Bootcamp.

Component	Description
Quarterly Updates: April 2024 – June 2024	<p data-bbox="391 174 1136 210">A. Has the SMART Objective changed? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="391 237 1412 268">■ Previous Objective (Archived): Submit five NSF CAREER proposals annually. <li data-bbox="391 289 1461 426">■ Rationale for Change: A recent institutional strategic shift deprioritized the NSF CAREER as a key benchmark for early career success. The research office has decided to focus more broadly on faculty readiness and submission of diverse federal proposals. <li data-bbox="391 447 1429 552">■ New SMART Objective: Deliver an annual proposal development institute to support submission of 15 competitive proposals to any federal agency by early career faculty. <li data-bbox="391 573 974 636">■ Are metrics and milestones also changing? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <p data-bbox="391 657 876 688">B. Have any of the following changed?</p> <p data-bbox="391 699 1396 762"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metrics <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Milestones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Major Activities <input type="checkbox"/> Sustainability Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Contextual Information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="391 793 1461 856">■ Description of Change: Metrics now reflect broader tracking of early-career federal submissions. Bootcamp has been expanded into a more inclusive institute. <p data-bbox="391 877 1477 1054">C. Emerging Learning: There is significant unmet demand for structured proposal support beyond the NSF CAREER. Faculty are more likely to engage when the training is not tied to a specific program and offers peer review, accountability sessions, and one-on-one consultations. Administrative buy-in remains strong, especially from the new VP for Research, who sees this as aligned with institutional growth goals.</p>

The background is a solid blue color with a complex, abstract pattern of thin, light blue lines that flow and curve across the page, creating a sense of movement and depth. A large, semi-transparent circular shape is visible in the lower right quadrant, partially overlapping the flowing lines.

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